

TEACHERS' PERCEPTIONS OF THE IMPACT OF TEENAGE PREGNANCY ON LEARNERS' ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE: A CASE OF SELECTED SCHOOLS IN SOUTH AFRICA

*Komape Mashuhlane*¹

*Letlhoyo Segalo*¹✉
lsegalo@cut.ac.za

*Tsakane Ngobeni*¹

¹*Department of Educational and Professional Studies
Central University of Technology
Welkom Campus, Robert Sobukwe Building, South Africa*

✉Corresponding author

Abstract

The purpose of this study was to investigate and describe the negative impact of teenage pregnancy on learners' academic performance in one district of education in South Africa. Teenage pregnancy was argued in the literature as the main source contributor to learners' low academic performance, especially in disadvantaged schools in South Africa. For example, teenage pregnant learners missed classes owing to absenteeism as they will be visiting clinics. Their performance rate fluctuates as this depends on their periodic mood swing, which they experience from time to time. In some cases, these teenage pregnant learners drop out of schools. The study followed a qualitative research approach where purposive sampling was employed to select two educators per institution from three selected schools. Pseudonyms were used to protect the participants from being known and encouraged them to participate freely. Trustworthiness and ethical considerations were adhered to. Open-ended questions were prepared and administered to the selected educators to find out the impact of teenage pregnancy on scholastic performance.

The study findings established that a sense of knowledge and respect of rights need to be promoted since these pregnant learners have the right to education and must receive the same education as other non-pregnant learners. The study, reported on this paper, further recommends that all stakeholders should discourage teenagers from watching television with sexual content that might tempt them to engage in sexual activities that can lead to teenage pregnancy, which will end up affecting their academic performance.

Keywords: Teenager, pregnancy, absenteeism, academic, performance, educator, rights of learners, education, drop out, stakeholders.

DOI: 10.21303/2504-5571.2023.002572

1. Introduction

Teenage pregnancy is pregnancy involving a woman of 19 years of age or younger [1]. It occurs after the start of ovulation, which can be before the first menstrual period but usually occurs after the onset of periods. Girls who fall pregnant during the said age frame are still at school. The problem of teenage pregnancy is caused by either lack of sexuality education or poverty [2]. Once these teenage learners become pregnant, they start to be absent from school to attend to prenatal consultations with their health practitioners to nurse their pregnancy. [3–5] state educators view teenage pregnancy as a problem because they are not trained to work with learners at a pregnancy stage.

Other learners in classroom situations also do not have the skill of coping with these pregnant learners. [6, 7] claim that teenage pregnancy is also caused by communication breakdown between parents and their children and peer pressure among other contributing factors. The study resolved the problem by suggesting abstinence. These pregnant teenage learners must attend school equally to other learners who are not pregnant. [8] stipulates that the pregnant teenager to equally be treated like others, while the latter section propagates the right to basic education. The problem the study reported on this paper sought to address the negative impact of teenage pregnancy on the scholastic performance of the concerned learners and other learners within the same classroom.

The impact of teenage pregnancy on learner academic performance was investigated along the following: classwork and homework assignments and tests and extra-co-curricular [9].

1. 1. Literature review

[1] asserts that building research on and relating it to existing knowledge is the building block of all academic research activities regardless of discipline. This helps to synthesise research findings to unravel areas, in which more research is needed. It is a way of identifying some gaps in the knowledge production. When reading an article, the reader maps and assesses the research area to motivate the aim of the study and justify the research question. In relation to the aforementioned information, there are so many source materials, published on teenage pregnancy. Many researchers focused on the causes, prevention and the impact of teenage pregnancy.

According to [10], teenagers who had sex before the age of 14 are likely to fall pregnant. This is evident in Vietnam, Asia where majority of adolescents become pregnant each year. These young girls who become pregnant are at risk of dropping out of school. [5] and [11] concur with [10] that pregnant adolescents are at risk of school dropout. America is said to be the leader of teenage pregnancy among the industrialised countries. The authors of this paper are now aware of the global status of teenage pregnancy. The problem is not unique to African countries. In all the two international continents, teenage pregnant learners are at risk of abridged education as compared to their peers. It would appear to be true, that learners who fall pregnant have limited chances of completing school. [12] further examined the relationship between adolescent pregnancy and educational attainment and concludes that adolescent pregnant learners perform poorly academically.

[13] posit that adolescents must have a reliable and trustworthy person to confide in. Having a knowledgeable person in an adolescent's life reduces the chances of teenage pregnancy. Parents must always teach their children about the body development and biological processes. This will help them understand the developmental process within their lives. Adolescents will develop a positive self-image and understand the environment, within which they find themselves.

Teenage pregnancy is a global problem and available in Africa. [14] conducted research on the impact of teenage pregnancy at a school in Namibia. Other African countries experience the problem of teenage pregnancy, and South Africa is not an exception. The aim of the study, reported on this paper, was investigate the impact of teenage pregnancy on learners' academic performance of Grade 7 learners in the Zambezi Region. The study revealed that teenagers get pregnant because of poor parental care and control. It is a taboo for some parents to talk about sexuality with their children. This ends up causing children to experiment with sex or ends up being either persuaded or robbed to engage in unprotected sex.

[15] conducted a study on the influence of teenage pregnancy on education. A qualitative research approach was followed with the use of interview questions to gain information from 12 educators at a high school in Tembisa, Gauteng Province to obtain their perceptions on how teenage pregnancy affected learner academic performance. The study revealed among others lack of communication between parents and children as a cause of teenage pregnancy. It was stressed, that children ended up exchanging sex for money with older men. Some other pregnancies are caused by lack of parental care, coupled with knowledge gap on contraceptives. Therefore, the authors investigated and described the negative impact of teenage pregnancy on learners' academic performance in selected schools in South Africa.

According to [10], sexual intercourse at or before the age of 14 correlated with high teenage pregnancy rate. This was evident in Vietnam where majority of adolescents aged 14 to 19 became pregnant each year. Young girls who become pregnant are at risk of abridged education. [11] highlights that the United States is the leader in adolescent pregnancy among industrialised nations. Again, [12] is of the view that pregnant adolescents are a population at risk of school dropout. These teenage pregnant learners are likely not to complete schooling as compared to their peers.

[14] conducted a study on the impact of teenage pregnancy on learners' academic performance in Namibia. The study aimed to find out the impact of teenage pregnancy on learners' academic performance of Grade 7 learners at a school in the Zambezi Region. The findings of the study revealed that teenagers get pregnant because of poor parental care and control. Poverty and poor peer guidance are the contributing factors to teenage pregnancy. Most learners fell pregnant because of lack of sex education. Alcohol and drug abuse are also factors behind teenage pregnancy.

The foregoing studies have strong points on addressing the impact of teenage pregnancy on learners' academic performance.

Aim of research was to explore teachers' perceptions of teenage pregnancy on learners' academic performance in selected schools in disadvantaged schools in South Africa.

2. Materials and methods

2. 1. Research Design

The research design used a qualitative, which according [16, 17] is applied on human experiences against a particular phenomenon. Data were recorded through a voice recorder and later transcribed. A semi-structured interview was used to illicit information and to gain insight into opinions and views of the participating teachers' respondents [18].

2. 2. Participant

Six Life Orientation educators were sampled using purposive sampling technique [17, 19]. There were three female and three male participants who participated in the study.

2. 3. Ethical Considerations

Participants participated voluntary and consented to the study without being forced [20, 21]. The research study was approved by the University Ethical Research Committee with a resolution reference FRIC 20/21/02.

2. 4. Data Analysis

Data were thematically analysed identifying patterns across qualitative data-sets [22]. The researcher arranged data according to the relatedness of ideas of what Life Orientation educators had been saying.

3. Results and Discussion

The results and findings of the study are discussed next, and the following sub-themes were raised: causes of teenage pregnancy, prevention of teenage pregnancy and teacher's approach to the problem of teenage pregnancy.

The causes of teenage pregnancy

The main causes of teenage pregnancy as stipulated from the research questions will be outlined next. The research found that the rate of teenage pregnancy in school B was high compared to A and C. This appeared to have been caused by cultural barriers where parents do not communicate sex issues with their children. Another contributory factor is the social media, which exposes these teenagers to the world of sex prematurely [23]. Children being given the responsibility of a parent may be too free to test whatever she would like to experience. Children who live in child-headed families are more likely to fall pregnant. Mother absence deprives the girl child the mother-daughter bond, which results in lack of advice, and the child ends up falling prey to teenage pregnancy. [23] express low community income level as a contributory factor to teenage pregnancy.

According to [24], teenagers living in poverty-stricken families are at risk of contracting teenage pregnancy. They might be tempted to engage in sex in exchange for money. In a puerile fashion, some would myopically fall pregnant with an aim of receiving social grant later. Social media plays a leading role to teenage pregnancy, especially when these teenagers watch movies with sexual content. They end up being tempted to experiment the sexual activity. Thobejane [6] observed that teenagers can sometimes be influenced by their peers to engage in sexual activities. Teenagers' lack of sex education is a major cause of teenage pregnancy. Poor knowledge on the use of contraceptives is another cause of teenage pregnancy.

At times teenagers fall pregnant because of being coerced to engage in sex or being raped by either stepfather or a relative (Naidoo, Muthukrishna and Nkabinde 2021). Teenagers from poor families with low educational aspiration are likely to fall pregnant. Teachers, parents and professional nurses must both teach sex education to rescue teenagers from becoming pregnant.

Prevention of teenage pregnancy in schools

The study discovered that schools only depended on Life Orientation educators to prevent teenage pregnancy. The majority of educators pleaded that advocacy should be held to make learners aware of the danger of teenage pregnancy on children's education [5, 7]. Parents are encouraged to take a stance in educating their children about the negative impact of teenage pregnancy on education not excluding other spheres like social, economic and health. Pastors together with teachers can help one another in preaching abstinence to teenagers to be safe from pregnancy and sexually transmitted diseases. Furthermore, [25] posit that teenagers should be taught on the use of contraceptives to prevent pregnancy. Interdepartmental awareness programmes need to be held frequently to prevent teenage pregnancy. Sex education should be the responsibility of both educators and parents. Parents must talk about sexuality whenever they are with their children. It is suggested, that educators should at least use the last three minutes of their contact time to teach about sex education.

Teachers approach to the problem of teenage pregnancy

Educators should see teenage pregnancy as a natural problem. Schools should allow pregnant learners to attend schooling during the pregnant stage. All stakeholders should talk about birth control methods like the use of condoms. There should be closer bond in families between parents and their children. Teenagers should have either a mentor from school and home to advise her. According to [26], educators should support pregnant learners and teach them without discriminating in either way or another. Schools should establish clinics where teenagers will get advice on sex education. Pregnant learners should be helped to cope with their situation. This is not permitting teenagers to engage in sex but would make them aware of protecting themselves from falling pregnant. Teenagers need to be taught the social values. Sex education should be taught at an early age, so that teenagers grow up knowing what is happening in their world. Teenagers must be taught the responsibilities and the aftermath of sex. Should a teenager miss the preventative measures and fall pregnant, the school must provide counselling.

Teenagers can be encouraged to participate in sports to avoid being lured into sexual attempts. Above all, teenagers should not submit to peer pressure. Educators should be friendly and patient with pregnant learners because their pregnancy might have been caused by rape or abuse by an elderly person from the family. It is possible, that these victims may not be ready to talk about their situation. These pregnant learners must not be discriminated against based on their status. More importantly, teachers must not tease them as this might affect their academic performance. Teachers and Learners' Representative Council should work on a policy on teenage pregnancy, which does not contradict the law of the country, the one that gives pregnant learners the right to education.

The influence of social media on teenage pregnancy

Media plays a very detrimental role in the life of the teenager. This statement is supported by [29] who indicate that teenagers who watch sexual content on television are more likely to experience teenage pregnancy. There was a study, conducted on the influence of social media on the teen's sexual behaviour as broadcasted on different media platforms. [30] also investigated the influence of social media on teenage pregnancy in secondary schools of Kenya. Adolescents are exposed to social media, which tempt them to experiment what they see.

Reflecting from the foregoing discussion, one may argue that access to social media has a negative impact when coming to teenagers, especially on matters related to sex.

Even some of the movies that teenagers watch prematurely prepare them to the world of sex. It is the responsibility of parents to control and restrict some certain programmes and channels from their children for protective reasons. According to [29], the mother-daughter relationship is much stronger than the relationship of other boy children. Sometimes the bond shifts during difficult times after the girl child shall have grown older.

Teenagers who watch movies and the television are more influenced by the sexual content. This makes them to compare their lives with those they watch on television. The sexual content, seen on television, impacts on teenagers' lives. Internet and television have an influence on teenage pregnancy. This teenage pregnancy has a negative effect on the learners' academic performance. Adolescents are affected by a multitude of mass media. These teenagers focus more on social media than on education. There are several programmes on television that teenagers are fond of watching. If they are not supervised on how long and which programmes are good for them, they might be negatively influenced to ignore their studies.

Teenagers will easily like to imitate what is portrayed on the media. The sexual content on television will influence teenagers to engage in sexual activities. Owing to this influence, teenagers need to be taught more on sex education. The question of abstinence, preventative measures, the causes of teenage pregnancy and the impact need to be unveiled to teenagers. The media shapes the ideas and beliefs of the mind of the teenager. What teenagers see on television with sexual content has a bad influence that can lead the teenager to become pregnant.

Social media can become a source of negative influence. If teenagers watch television for a long time, their academic achievement may drop. Both girls and boys can be the victims of social media, should they spend more time on it. Watching sexual content may eventually lead teenagers to a life of motherhood after teenage pregnancy rather than focusing on their future. To avoid motherhood, some resort to abortion to avoid stigmatisation. Social media is a contributory factor responsible for teenage pregnancy in the society. It affects all age groups but adolescents are more vulnerable than other groups. This will make their academic performance to drop.

Media, communication and educational technology lead to teenage pregnancy. Social media results in an increased rate of teenage pregnancy. The influence of social media on teenage pregnancy among learners is more on sexual music videos and images, which in turn negatively impact on the life of teenagers culminating in teenage pregnancy. However, the use of social media is not always bad; it depends on the quality of the content the child is watching. It can also be positive when teenagers are supervised on the use of media including television and social media.

Teachers help pregnant learners

Educators need to encourage pregnant learners not to give up as they now have somebody coming who will depend on them. The school should also invite social workers and professional nurses to talk to these learners. [26] indicates that educators should receive in service training on how to deal with pregnant learners. Parents of these learners should be summoned to the school to get advice on how to handle them. Parents and learners must be helped to accept the situation. These pregnant learners must be supported emotionally, physically, educationally, and socially. Both educators and learners should not discriminate pregnant learners.

Educators must establish a healthy connection with learners. Irrespective of the pregnant situation, educators should create a good rapport with their learners and this will make them become more adjusting to the problem of teenage pregnancy. Educators must reward good behaviour in class, especially when a pregnant learner behaves well.

Educators should allow expectant learners to leave their classrooms three minutes before the end of the lesson to avoid congestion with the group [26]. Teachers should be open with pregnant learners, their fathers and their families. Teachers can further advise with regard to clothing that would better suit the situation of the pregnant learner. In cases where the expectant learner misses a lesson, a missed activity needs to be given to the learner. If the pregnant learner has morning complications, she would be allowed to report late.

Teachers need to provide counselling in supporting the pregnant learner. Where information is given, the teacher should be cautious not to divulge it to people. The information shared should be kept confidential. If the pregnant learner is sick, special concessions can be made for her with regard to writing examination. The teacher can help the expectant learner with the choice of friends who will support her with school work. Teachers must be sensitive not calling the expectant learners by names like you “big tummy” as this will make her insecure in the class.

The expectant learners cannot manage all physical activities during Life Orientation programmes. Educators should ensure that some of the activities do not include participation by pregnant learners.

Educators can start a newsletter containing advice to help teenage pregnant learners to cope with their situation [30]. Some of the pregnant learners might drop out from school and as such, job training should be provided. This will help the teenage mother to have plans to cater for the baby. Educators should work with the community to encourage them to employ teenage mother, should a community-based programme be initiated [31, 32]. Teachers should organise subsidy on day care for children of poor teenage mothers. They can also motivate minor parents to live with an adult responsible for caring for her baby. The nutritional knowledge should be provided for the teenage mother to reduce low birth weight of the baby.

The research was limited to the qualitative approach and the size of the sample was very small. Again, the study was based on few selected schools in the area researched. Future research should not be too narrow on the specific population, but instead should be inclusive of all Life Orientation educators and employ a bit of snowballing to access more information on teacher perceptions on teenage pregnancy on their academic performance. Furthermore, future studies should include school teenage pregnant learners on how they cope with their academic performance.

4. Conclusion

This paper reported on the negative impact of teenage pregnancy on learners' academic performance and presented the findings and the recommendations of the study. Deployment of professional nurses and social workers at schools to help the pregnant learners is critical. Since the main objective of this study was to investigate the impact of teenage pregnancy in schools, it was found, that teenage pregnancy has a bad influence on the academic achievement. All stakeholders need to work together to address this problem. It emerged from the research process that participants are trying to work collectively to render service towards improving the future of these learners. It was also evident, that if all can join hands, maybe this problem can be curbed if not minimised.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest in relation to this paper, as well as the published research results, including the financial aspects of conducting the research, obtaining and using its results, as well as any non-financial personal relationships.

Funding

This research study was funded by Faculty of Humanities Research and Innovative Committee of the Central University of Technology, Free State.

References

- [1] Ramulumo, M. R., Pitsoe, V. J. (2013). Teenage Pregnancy in South African Schools: Challenges, Trends and Policy Issues. *Mediterranean Journal of Social Sciences*, 4 (13), 755–755. doi: <https://doi.org/10.5901/mjss.2013.v4n13p755>
- [2] Field, S., Abrahams, Z., Honikman, S. (2020). Adolescent mothers: A qualitative study on barriers and facilitators to mental health in a low-resource setting in Cape Town, South Africa. *African Journal of Primary Health Care & Family Medicine*, 12 (1). doi: <https://doi.org/10.4102/phcfm.v12i1.2279>
- [3] Jochim, J., Cluver, L. D., Meinck, F. (2021). Learner pregnancy in South Africa's Eastern Cape: The Factors affecting adolescent girls' school withdrawal during pregnancy. *International Journal of Educational Development*, 87, 102484. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijedudev.2021.102484>
- [4] Barron, P., Subedar, H., Letsoko, M., Makua, M., Pillay, Y. (2022). Teenage births and pregnancies in South Africa, 2017 – 2021 – a reflection of a troubled country: Analysis of public sector data. *South African Medical Journal*, 112 (4), 252–258. doi: <https://doi.org/10.7196/samj.2022.v112i4.16327>
- [5] Segalo, L. (2020). Learner pregnancy in secondary schools in South Africa: Have attitudes and perceptions of teachers changed? *Koers – Bulletin for Christian Scholarship*, 85 (1). doi: <https://doi.org/10.19108/koers.85.1.2461>
- [6] Thobejane, T. D. (2015). Factors Contributing to Teenage Pregnancy in South Africa: The Case of Matjijileng Village. *Journal of Sociology and Social Anthropology*, 6 (2), 273–277. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1080/09766634.2015.11885667>
- [7] Madzamba, R. (2022). Socio-economic Factors Associated with Teenage Pregnancy in the Mandela Park Community of Mthatha, South Africa. *Commonwealth Youth and Development*, 19 (1). doi: <https://doi.org/10.25159/2663-6549/9464>
- [8] South Africa (Republic) *South African Schools Act*, 86 (1996). Pretoria: Government Press.
- [9] Snyder, H. (2019). Literature review as a research methodology: An overview and guidelines. *Journal of Business Research*, 104, 333–339. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2019.07.039>
- [10] Nguyen, H., Shiu, C., Farber, N. (2016). Prevalence and Factors Associated with Teen Pregnancy in Vietnam: Results from Two National Surveys. *Societies*, 6 (2), 17. doi: <https://doi.org/10.3390/soc6020017>
- [11] Humberstone, E. (2019). Friendship networks and adolescent pregnancy: Examining the potential stigmatization of pregnant teens. *Network Science*, 7 (4), 523–540. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1017/nws.2019.25>
- [12] Humberstone, E. (2018). Dynamics of Social Networks Following Adolescent Pregnancy. *Journal of Social Structure*, 19 (1), 1–34. doi: <https://doi.org/10.21307/joss-2018-009>

- [13] Odu, B. K., Ayodele, C. J. (2006). The Incidence of Teenage Pregnancy in Ekiti State, Nigeria. *Nigerian Journal of Guidance and Counselling*, 11 (1). doi: <https://doi.org/10.4314/njgc.v11i1.36987>
- [14] Maemeko, E. L., Nkengbeza, D., Chokomosi, T. M. (2018). The Impact of Teenage Pregnancy on Academic Performance of Grade 7 Learners at a School in the Zambezi Region. *Open Journal of Social Sciences*, 6 (9), 88–100. doi: <https://doi.org/10.4236/jss.2018.69006>
- [15] Nkosi, N. N., Pretorius, E. (2019). The influence of teenage pregnancy on education: perceptions of educators at a secondary school in Tembisa, Gauteng. *Social Work*, 55 (1). doi: <https://doi.org/10.15270/55-1-698>
- [16] Ankomah, A., Konadu Gyesaw, N. Y. (2013). Experiences of pregnancy and motherhood among teenage mothers in a suburb of Accra, Ghana: a qualitative study. *International Journal of Women's Health*, 5, 773. doi: <https://doi.org/10.2147/ijwh.s51528>
- [17] Mangeli, M., Rayyani, M., Cheraghi, M. A., Tirgari, B. (2017). Exploring the challenges of adolescent mothers from their life experiences in the transition to motherhood: a qualitative study. *Journal of family & reproductive health*, 11 (3), 165–173.
- [18] Nandra, R., Brockie, A. F., Hussain, F. (2020). A review of informed consent and how it has evolved to protect vulnerable participants in emergency care research. *EFORT Open Reviews*, 5 (2), 73–79. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1302/2058-5241.5.180051>
- [19] Kakilla, C. (2021). Strengths and weaknesses of semi-structured interviews in qualitative research: A critical essay. doi: <https://doi.org/10.20944/preprints202106.0491.v1>
- [20] Lester, J. N., Cho, Y., Lochmiller, C. R. (2020). Learning to Do Qualitative Data Analysis: A Starting Point. *Human Resource Development Review*, 19 (1), 94–106. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1177/1534484320903890>
- [21] Brinkmann, S., Kvale, S. (2017). Ethics in qualitative psychological research. *The Sage handbook of qualitative research in psychology*, 259–273. doi: <https://doi.org/10.4135/9781526405555.n15>
- [22] Bailey, J. (2008). First steps in qualitative data analysis: transcribing. *Family Practice*, 25 (2), 127–131. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1093/fampra/cmn003>
- [23] Mohr, R., Carbajal, J., Sharma, B. B. (2019). The Influence of Educational Attainment on Teenage Pregnancy in Low-Income Countries: A Systematic Literature Review. *Journal of Social Work in the Global Community*, 4 (1). doi: <https://doi.org/10.5590/jswgc.2019.04.1.02>
- [24] Lambani, M. N. (2015). Poverty the Cause of Teenage Pregnancy in Thulamela Municipality. *Journal of Sociology and Social Anthropology*, 6 (2). doi: <https://doi.org/10.31901/24566764.2015/06.02.01>
- [25] Masemola-Yende, J. P. F., Mataboge, S. M. (2015). Access to information and decision making on teenage pregnancy prevention by females in Tshwane. *Curationis*, 38 (2). doi: <https://doi.org/10.4102/curationis.v38i2.1540>
- [26] Matlala, S. F. (2017). Ethical issues related to research on pregnant school-going teenagers in South Africa. *African Population Studies*, 31 (1). doi: <https://doi.org/10.11564/31-1-957>
- [27] Kiarie, A. K., Mugambi, M. M. (2016). Social Media and Teenage Pregnancy among Students in Secondary Schools In Imenti North Sub-County, Meru County, Kenya. *International Journal of Scientific Research and Management*, 4 (9), 4586–4606. doi: <https://doi.org/10.18535/ijserm/v4i9.18>
- [28] Barney, A., Rodriguez, F., Schwarz, E. B., Reed, R., Tancredi, D., Brindis, C. D. et al. (2021). Adapting to Changes in Teen Pregnancy Prevention Research: Social Media as an Expedited Recruitment Strategy. *Journal of Adolescent Health*, 69 (2), 349–353. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jadohealth.2020.12.140>
- [29] Adolescent pregnancy (2020). World Health Organization. Available at: <https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/adolescent-pregnancy>.
- [30] Mathebula, R. N., Runhare, T., Mafumo, T. N. (2022). Educational support for pregnant and parenting schoolgirls in rural South African school settings. *Issues in Educational Research*, 32 (2), 593–612.
- [31] Mathebula, R. N. (2019). School-based interventions into effects of schoolgirl pregnancy on teaching and learning in Mopani District, Limpopo Province, South Africa. University of Venda.
- [32] Opondo, C. M., Aloka, P. J. O. (2022). Effect of school category on adjustment of re-admitted teenage mothers in secondary schools. *ScienceRise*, 3, 48–56. doi: <https://doi.org/10.21303/2313-8416.2022.002534>

Received date 27.09.2022

Accepted date 27.12.2022

Published date 31.01.2023

© The Author(s) 2022

This is an open access article under the
Creative Commons CC BY license

How to cite: Ogwu, K., Naicker, V. (2023). *The role of information technology innovations on organisational performance: a case study of selected SMEs. EUREKA: Social and Humanities, 1, 54–60.* doi: <http://doi.org/10.21303/2504-5571.2023.002760>